

Microplastics in the realm of Svalbard: current knowledge and future perspective (MIREs II)

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1. Introduction

Plastic pollution has emerged as a global threat (MacLeod et al. 2021). The exponential increase in plastic production has resulted in widespread contamination (Rochman et al. 2013). Plastics, including microplastics (MPs) (<5 mm), mesoplastic (5 mm–2.5 cm), macroplastic (2.5 cm–1 m) and megaplastic (>1 m), have infiltrated every corner of the planet, from urban centres to remote areas, including the Arctic.

Arctic regions face significant challenges from human-induced factors, including climate change, (Meredith et al. 2019; Zemp et al. 2019), pollution (Dietz et al. 2019), and invasive species (Goldsmith et al. 2018). MPs have emerged as an additional complicating factor (Halsband and Herzke 2019; Kim et al. 2023), further straining these already stressed environments (Figure 1). In our previous chapter (Singh et al. 2021), we examined the status of MPs pollution in Svalbard, identifying research gaps and emphasizing the importance of regular monitoring of MPs levels. We also highlighted the need to understand their sources and impacts. Since then, new insights into MPs in Svalbard have emerged. For example, one study on algae suggested MPs integration into Arctic food chains (Bergmann et al. 2023). Another study detected MPs in water, sediment, and even walruses (Carlsson et al. 2021), emphasizing their widespread presence and impact on Arctic wildlife. By referencing Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) reports (AMAP 2021a, 2021b),

and incorporating these new findings, this updated chapter aims to advance our understanding of this issue in Svalbard, and potentially prompt effective measures to protect the fragile ecosystems of Svalbard and the Arctic as a whole.

Figure 1: Plastic pollution in Svalbard (Photo: Geir Wing Gabrielsen)

2. The state of MPs in different environmental compartments

Atmosphere: Research on atmospheric MPs is expanding, with evidence of their dispersion in the atmosphere from various global locations like the Ecuadorian Andes, French Pyrenees, Italian Alps, U.S. conservation areas, Arctic snow, Nunavut in the Canadian Arctic, and Germany's Isle of Helgoland. However, since the study by Bergmann

et al. (2019), nothing has been published on atmospheric MPs in Svalbard, highlighting the need for further investigation.

Ice and Snow: Kanhai et al. (2020) updated our understanding of MPs in Arctic Central Basin sea ice cores and underlying waters (Appendix 1).

Lower MPs concentrations were found in surface waters (0-18 particles/m³) (n=22) compared to sea ice cores (2-17 particles/L) (n=22). No consistent vertical distribution was observed in the sea ice cores. These findings suggest the Siberian shelves, seas in the western Arctic, and the Central Arctic Basin as potential sources of MPs. Understanding MPs in Arctic Ocean compartments is vital for assessing risks to polar organisms. Despite study limitations, these authors highlight the Arctic Sea ice's role as a complex MPs reservoir, source, and transport pathway.

Open Ocean: Since our previous chapter, four new studies have provided additional insights into the distribution of MPs in the Arctic Ocean and adjacent waters (Appendix 1). Tošić et al. (2020) explored the Barents Sea, revealing a wide range of MPs concentrations, varying from 0.97 to 6.42 items/m³ (n=3). These variations were influenced by complex oceanic patterns and fishing activities. Yakushev et al. (2021) sampled waters in the Eurasian Arctic. They reported an average of 0.004 item/m³ (n=48) in surface samples and 0.8 item/m³ (n=60) in subsurface samples. This study also unveiled differences in MPs characteristics among various water masses, suggesting their potential as regional markers. Pakhomova et al. (2022) conducted a comparative analysis across regions, highlighting significantly elevated MPs concentrations ranging from 7–7.5 µg/m³ in the Central Atlantic and the Barents Sea, in contrast to the North Atlantic and Siberian Arctic Ocean with concentrations of 0.6 µg/m³. These findings underscore the diverse sources, distribution patterns, and influencing factors contributing to MPs presence in these waters. In a more recent study, Emberson-Mar et al. (2023) focused on the Barents Sea, collecting subsurface water samples along transects. They found MPs concentrations ranging 0.007–0.015 m³ (n=6). Notably, this study detected higher concentrations closer to land and towards the ice edge, attributed to factors like melting sea ice and long-range transport from Europe.

Fjord and Bay Waters: Two studies investigated MPs in fjords and coastal waters following the MIREs project (Appendix 1). Bao et al. (2022)

studied surface water (0–0.4 m) and water column (0–200 m) of Rjipfjorden, identifying a total of 1,010 MPs particles and 14 mesoplastics among the 41,038 particles analysed. The range of MPs was 0.15 ± 0.19 n/m³ in surface water (n=6) and 0.15 ± 0.03 n/m³ in the water column (n=2). This study identified 10 different polymers, including polyurethane, polyethylene, polyvinyl acetate, polystyrene, polypropylene, and alkyd varnish. It is believed that melting sea ice contributes to the presence of MPs, with alkyd varnish (accounting for 49%) suggesting shipping activities as a significant source. Kaliszewicz et al. (2023) collected water samples from six bays in the Barents Sea and freshwater lakes in the remote Kola Peninsula to investigate MPs contamination in this isolated Arctic region. MPs were found in all samples (n=18), with levels below 4,800 items/m³ in the Barents Sea and below 3,900 items/m³ in the lakes. Contributing factors to MPs presence in the lakes included landfill waste, protective clothing, and wind dispersion. The Norwegian Current played a pivotal role in transporting contaminants and MPs to the studied bays within the Barents Sea.

Freshwater: No new information has emerged concerning MPs in freshwater lakes in Svalbard since our previous report was published. It is essential to address this knowledge gap to gain a comprehensive understanding of MPs sources, their fate in Arctic lakes, and potential environmental consequences.

Sediment: Four new studies expanded our knowledge of MPs in sediment (Appendix 1). Choudhary et al. (2022) studied MPs in Krossfjorden and Kongsfjorden, finding high concentrations of 721 ± 218 (n=5) and 783 ± 530 (n=8) pieces/kg dry weight (dw) respectively. Predominant polymers were polyethylene and polypropylene, mainly fibrous. Other common polymers like polyvinylchloride and nitrile were also present, primarily in the 0.3–1 mm range. This study concluded that despite Svalbard's isolation and sparse population, the Krossfjord–Kongsfjord system showed MPs contamination from various sources such as ocean currents, sea ice, glacial melt, wind, and local human activities. Ramasamy

et al. (2021) studied sediment from different locations in Kongsfjorden and found 4 to 24 MPs/kg (dw) sediment. This study stressed the need for source identification, deposition mechanisms, and understanding of MP effects in Arctic fjords. Lin et al. (2022) studied MPs and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in Svalbard's Kongsfjorden and Rijpfjorden using surface sediment samples. They found only fibrous MPs in a range from non-detectable (ND) to 4.936 particles/kg (n=8) in Rijpfjorden and in Kongsfjorden from ND to 2.218 particles/kg. Three fibrous polymers were detected – polyester, rayon, and cellulose – suggesting that fishing debris and textiles may contribute to MPs pollution in these fjords. Kongsfjorden exhibited a stronger anthropogenic influence, while Rijpfjorden's MPs distribution seemed more influenced by ocean currents. Collard et al. (2021) studied surface sediment and core samples from Kongsfjorden to quantify anthropogenic particles (APs), including MPs. In surface sediment, APs averaged 0.33 ± 0.05 item 100 g^{-1} (dw), with MPs averaging 0.17 ± 0.04 item 100 g^{-1} (n=68). Sediment cores showed higher AP and MPs concentrations, averaging 1.34 ± 0.21 and 0.75 ± 0.12 item 100 g^{-1} . AP and MPs pollution in Kongsfjorden is mainly attributed to a sewage outlet in Ny-Ålesund. Interestingly, the site closest to the outlet had lower APs levels, possibly due to transport and accumulation in an eddy. The fjord's mouth, near the eddy, was the most polluted site in terms of APs. Roughly half of the APs were MPs, while the rest were primarily dyed fibres. This highlights the significant role of Kongsfjorden's currents in APs distribution within the sediment. These studies collectively emphasize the prevalence and sources of MPs in Arctic fjords, underlining the need for further research to understand their environmental impacts on these sensitive ecosystems.

Terrestrial environment: MPs are widespread in various environments, including the cryosphere and atmosphere. However, research gap from Svalbard's terrestrial areas is sparse. Our previous chapter stressed the need for terrestrial MPs studies here. Studying these environments is vital for assessing potential MPs risks. Notably, Hallanger et al. (2022) explored the presence of human litter, including

plastic, in Arctic foxes (*Vulpes lagopus*), finding several pieces of a sour cream carton within one stomach.

2.1. Climate change and MPs distributions

In our previous chapter, we discussed how climate change, including shifting patterns, melting ice and glaciers, thawing permafrost, weather alterations, ocean current shifts, and ecosystem changes, affect MPs distribution in the Arctic. We also examined the melting cryosphere's role as a temporary MPs source. Now, we aim to delve deeper into the climate change–MPs relationship, moving beyond just how climate change influences MPs. Climate change and plastic pollution are interconnected and several climate-induced changes are known to influence the concentrations and distribution of plastic in the world (Bergmann et al. 2022). Understanding this connection can enhance our approach to tackling both issues. Hence, future research should focus on their combined environmental impact.

2.1.1. **MPs and the carbon cycle: a growing concern**

One pressing concern is how plastic production, closely tied to the consumption of oil, worsens climate change by creating greenhouse gases (UNEP, 2021). Plastics have accumulated in the environment to become a globally significant pool of organic carbon (Stubbins et al., 2021). Here is why this matters: in Arctic areas, permafrost holds a vast amount of organic carbon in the soil. But as it thaws due to climate change, it releases trapped MPs, turning permafrost from a carbon sink into a carbon source (Chen et al. 2021). Microbial activity also plays a role in this release, adding complexity to the MPs–carbon cycle interaction. Therefore, studying MPs in permafrost is crucial for future research. In oceans, MPs serve as surfaces for microbes to grow and form biofilms, which increases organic carbon production and results in gel-like particles (Galgani et al. 2019). While microbial communities on MPs can impact greenhouse gas cycling, their contribution to

global gas surface inventories appears relatively low (Cornejo-D'Ottone et al. 2020). Nevertheless, MPs can influence the biogeochemical cycles of oceans, affecting consumers' exposure and the environmental fate of MPs (Rogers et al. 2020). Additionally, MPs alter the composition and function of microbial communities in ocean sediments, affecting carbon cycling (Seeley et al. 2020).

2.1.2. MPs and climate risk: examining the relationship

MPs pose a potential climatic risk in cryospheric regions. Studies show that cryosphere melting depends on temperature, precipitation, and the presence of light-absorbing particles like black carbon and mineral dust (Farinotti et al. 2020; Yao et al. 2022). These particles darken snow surfaces, reduce albedo (reflectivity), and accelerate melting (Kang et al. 2020). For example, increased black carbon in Arctic regions has led to reduced sea ice and intensified warming (Flanner et al. 2007; Li and Flanner 2018). MPs, like black carbon, can absorb radiation and lower albedo, hastening cryosphere melting (Revell et al. 2021). This suggests that MPs within snow may reduce glacier surface albedo, further impacting the energy balance. As glaciers melt faster, MPs could enter rivers and lakes downstream, posing ecological risks. Currently, we lack comprehensive research on the effects of airborne MPs on surface snow. Additionally, in marine environments, MPs can influence water temperatures and physicochemical properties, potentially initiating climate feedback cycles in ocean surface layers (VishnuRadhan et al. 2019).

Significantly, we still need to learn about the climatic effects of MPs on snow and ice. Questions about MPs properties, impact on radiation absorption, and comparison with particles like black carbon and dust remain. Addressing these knowledge gaps requires further research into how MPs affect cryosphere regions.

2.2. Update on food safety

Updating our understanding of the sociological impacts of MPs, particularly concerning food safety in the Arctic, is crucial. Indigenous Arctic populations have a deep historical connection to Arctic ecosystems, and possess a wealth of knowledge related to their environment. Their traditional way of life, heavily reliant on hunting and fishing for sustenance, makes them particularly vulnerable to the presence of pollutants, including MPs, in their surroundings. In contrast, Svalbard's population has access to alternative sources of traditional wild foods, such as supplies from Svalbardbutikken and mainland Norway. This diversity in food sources introduces complexity when attempting to predict how MPs are transferred to the population in Svalbard, especially through locally hunted wildlife. In Svalbard, our current understanding of MPs exposure, bioaccumulation, and the impact of consumption of locally hunted wild foods is limited. Addressing these knowledge gaps will contribute significantly to enhancing our comprehension of the potential risks associated with traditional food consumption in Svalbard, particularly in the context of MP contamination and its implications for food safety.

3. Contributions to interdisciplinarity

The issue of microplastics extends beyond specific environments; it is a widespread concern observed across all environmental compartments. Within this context, this chapter not only synthesizes updated knowledge of the microplastic pollution status in Svalbard but also identifies specific areas for further interdisciplinary research and outlines future focal

points (see recommendations section).

Importantly, a recommendation from Singh et al. (2021) has been implemented in a master's thesis, contributing to refining methodologies for studying microplastics in the Arctic (Brenden 2021).

4. Unanswered questions

Three years after the first MIREs chapter was published, our knowledge has improved but not enough to answer all the questions raised there. No specific topic has attracted the interest and focus of scientific research within the field of microplastic pollution in the Arctic. The lack of development globally is undoubtedly due to the remoteness and consequent high cost of sample collection there. In particular, research on terrestrial ecosystems and/or biota is likely more challenging than marine research as the latter is usually performed on ships where working conditions are better. Here it is important to highlight that AMAP is actively developing a monitoring plan to identify essential elements and considerations for a well-coordinated environmental monitoring program focused on litter and microplastics throughout the Arctic (AMAP 2021a).

Trends: Tracking trends of MPs across different environmental compartments proves challenging due to inconsistencies in sampling methods, data protocols, lack of comprehensive data and inaccurate categorization of natural or semi-artificial polymers. Further, each study is only one point in time and can be challenging to incorporate into a holistic understanding without vast amount of data.

Sources: The sources of MPs in the Arctic are both local and long-range. Differentiating between local or long-range sources is often not possible, and the smaller the particle the less likely a source will be identified. There is a need to fully understand and to quantify possible local pollution to be able to theoretically differentiate between local and long-range sources.

Toxicological effects and ecological risks: While MPs have been identified in marine organisms, the consequences arising from plastic additives and pollutants are poorly understood. There are several experimental studies showing both toxic and non-toxic behaviour, though linking this knowledge to environmental samples or scenarios is difficult due to multiple exposure pathways and cocktail mixtures.

Fate in extreme Arctic conditions: Uncertainty exists about how MPs transform and accumulate in Svalbard's extreme Arctic conditions. The interactions between MPs and Arctic ecosystems' physical and biological elements are poorly explored, leading to unpredictable environmental effects.

Climate change and plastic dynamics: While climate change is altering the physical environment in Svalbard, its specific effects on plastic cycling and transformation in the region are not well understood and require further investigation.

Food safety and human health concerns: Limited documentation of MPs in harvested wildlife and fish raises questions about potential human health risks from ingestion and inhalation of MPs. Notably, the widespread use of clothing made from plastic fibres in Svalbard may release particles into the air over time, adding concerns about human long-term plastic exposure.

Air-to-ecosystem exchange: The transfer of MPs from the air to marine and terrestrial environments is an understudied area, leaving gaps in our understanding of how these particles move through ecosystems.

5. Recommendations for the future

The importance of long-term monitoring of plastic pollution on a global scale cannot be overstated,

especially when we consider places like Svalbard. Despite its remote location, Svalbard is not immune

to the effects of global plastic pollution. The plastic litter found in Svalbard is a symptom of a much larger, global problem. Long-term monitoring allows us to track the sources and pathways of plastic pollution, understand its impact on various ecosystems, and measure the effectiveness of mitigation strategies. It provides the data necessary to inform policy decisions and drive international cooperation. Ultimately, plastic pollution in Svalbard serves as a stark reminder that our actions have global consequences, reinforcing the need for sustained, global monitoring efforts.

Harmonization: Convene a workshop with experts on plastic pollution in Svalbard to come to agreements on a monitoring framework. This should be aligned with and incorporated into the AMAP Programme since standardizing and harmonizing methods is pivotal not only for Svalbard, but also for uniformity across the pan-Arctic and globally.

Collaboration: Establish a Svalbard plastic task

force. Its members should meet regularly to develop methods and monitoring recommendations to ensure a concerted effort to fulfil knowledge gaps.

Mapping: Conduct a thorough mapping of MPs in Svalbard, including biota from both terrestrial and marine ecosystems. Mapping is necessary to establish reliable risk assessment and monitoring guidelines for the environment and human consumers.

Long-term monitoring: A monitoring programme should be designed to include societal needs. Scientists working on MPs can provide advice regarding plastic use in Svalbard, wastewater treatment, effects of recreational (cruises/tourists) and fishing activities.

Experiments: Experimental studies on MPs effects on Arctic key species should be promoted and the possible trophic transfer of MPs under Arctic conditions should be investigated.

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Manta sampler to collect plastic particles (MP) at the sea surface, June 2021 on a 'plastic research cruise' with RV Kronprins Haakon in Isfjorden, Svalbard. (Photo: Geir Wing Gabrielsen, NPI)

Appendix 1: MPs in different abiotic compartments of Svalbard

Location	Year	Medium	Concentration	Unit	Size range	Sampling method	Analytical method	Reference
Ice and Snow								
Arctic Sea Central Basin	2016	Sea ice core	2-17	particles/L	0.10-4.99 mm	Ice coring	Microscope (Olympus SZX10) equipped with a polariser and camera (Q Imaging Retiga 2000R) and Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy	Kanghai et al. (2020)
Ocean								
Arctic Sea Central Basin	2016	Sea water under ice floe	0-18	particles/m ³	0.25-5 mm	Pump	Microscope (Olympus SZX10) equipped with a polariser and camera (Q Imaging Retiga 2000R) and Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy	Kanghai et al. (2020)
Barents Sea	2018	Surface water	0.97 to 6.42	items/m ³	> 5 mm	Manta trawl	Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy	Tošić et al. (2020)
Barents Sea	2019	Surface water	0.004 (avg)	item/m ³	0.2-5 mm	Neuston net	Nikon D750 camera and Tamron SP AF 28-75/2.8 XR LD lens and Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)	Yakushev et al. (2021)
Barents Sea	2019	Subsurface water	0.8 (avg)	item/m ³	0.1-3.6 mm	Pump	Nikon D750 camera and Tamron SP AF 28-75/2.8 XR LD lens and Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)	Yakushev et al. (2021)
Central Atlantic and Barents Sea	September 2019-February 2020	Subsurface water	7-7.5	µg/m ³	0.1-4.9 mm	Pump	Microscope (Nikon SMZ745xT; 20 × magnification), and Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (µFT-IR)	Pakhomova et al. (2022)
Barents Sea	2018	Subsurface water	0.007-0.015	Microplastics/m ³	0 - > 5000 µm	Pump	Olympus (SZX16) microscope (x25 magnification) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR; PerkinElmer Spotlight 400).	Emberson-Mar et al. (2023)
Fjord and bay waters								
Rijpfjorden	2017	Surface water (0-0.4 m)	0.15±0.19	n/m ³	200.1-4694.1 µm	Manta net	Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) technique and Laser Direct Infrared	Bao et al. (2022)
Rijpfjorden	2017	Water column (0-200 m)	0.15±0.03	n/m ³	200.1-4694.1 µm	Manta net	Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) technique and Laser Direct Infrared	Bao et al. (2022)
Barents Sea	2019	Surface water	4,800 items/m ³	items/m ³	0.01-5mm	Plankton net	Raman spectroscopy	Kaliszewicz et al. (2023)

Sediment		Year	Location	Concentration	Size	Sampler	Method	Reference
Kongsfjorden	Surface sediment	2016	Surface sediment	783±530.28	0.3–1 mm	Van Veen Grab sampler	Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FT-IR) and Perkin-Elmer PC-16 FT-IR spectrometer	Choudhary et al. (2022)
Krossfjorden	Surface sediment	2016	Surface sediment	721.42±217.89	0.3–1 mm	Van Veen Grab sampler	Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) and Perkin-Elmer PC-16 FT-IR spectrometer	Choudhary et al. (2022)
Kongsfjorden	Surface sediment	2016	Surface sediment	4–24	55–381 µm	Van Veen Grab sampler	Microscope (Zeiss Stemi 508) and Raman spectrometer (WITec Alpha 300RA, Germany)	Ramasamy et al. (2021)
Kongsfjorden	Surface sediment	2017	Surface sediment	ND–2.218		Box corer	Visual identification by microscope (ZEISS, Scope A1, Germany) Micro Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (µFT-IR)	Lin et al. (2022)
Rijpfjorden	Surface sediment	2017	Surface sediment	ND–4.936	NA	Box corer	Microscope (ZEISS, Scope A1, Germany) and Micro Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (µFT-IR)	Lin et al. (2022)
Kongsfjorden	Surface sediment and 5 cm core	2018	Surface sediment and 5 cm core	0.17±0.04 (avg) (items)	0.10–6.31 mm	Box corer	LabRam 300 spectrometer (Horiba Jobin-Yvon) d with an Olympus BX 40 confocal microscope and Fourier-Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)	Collard et al. (2021)

ND=Not Detectable; NA=Information is not available in the manuscript

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